

LSN-Based Copy-on-Write Database Branching on LSM-Tree Storage with Delta SSTables and Multi-Strategy Merge

Daniel Moya
daniel.moya@dimensigon.com
Dimensigon

26 March 2026

Publication Type: Defensive Publication – Prior Art Disclosure

Classification: cs.DB (Databases)

License: CC-BY-4.0

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19242706

Abstract

We describe an implementation of git-like database branching on top of LSM-tree (Log-Structured Merge-tree) storage using RocksDB. Unlike existing database branching implementations that use custom storage formats (Dolt’s proly trees), distributed storage layers (Neon), or block-level snapshots (Simplyblock Vela), our approach implements page-level copy-on-write using Delta SSTables within the LSM-tree architecture. Branches are created in sub-millisecond time as metadata-only operations (256 bytes). Read operations traverse a four-layer hierarchy: branch memtable, branch Delta SSTables, parent Delta SSTables, and shared SSTables. The system supports seven merge strategies (Ours, Theirs, Manual, RuleBased, LastWriteWins, Custom UDF, Abort) with three-way merge conflict detection. Each branch maintains independent MVCC snapshots with SERIALIZABLE isolation. This disclosure establishes prior art for LSM-tree-specific database branching with Delta SSTables.

1 Introduction

Git-like database branching is offered by multiple systems: Dolt [1] uses proly trees with content-addressed storage; Neon [2] separates compute and storage with COW at the storage layer; PlanetScale [3] offers schema-only branching; Databricks Lakebase [4] uses COW for OLTP; Simplyblock Vela uses block-level COW on Kubernetes.

However, implementing branching on LSM-tree storage engines (RocksDB, LevelDB) presents unique challenges and opportunities:

- LSM-trees already use immutable SSTables, naturally suited for sharing across branches
- Memtables provide natural per-branch write buffers
- Compaction must be made branch-aware (see companion paper DP-MVCC001)
- The append-only nature of LSM writes enables efficient delta tracking

2 Architecture

2.1 Branch Metadata

Each branch stores: branch ID, parent branch ID, creation LSN, current LSN, state (Active/Merged/-Dropped), and a merge strategy default.

2.2 Delta SSTable Format

Branch-specific modifications are stored in Delta SSTables with the format:

```
1 Header:
2   Magic: 0x48454C4942 ("HELIB")
3   Version: 1
4   Branch ID: UUID (16 bytes)
5   LSN Range: (start_lsn, end_lsn)
6   Index Offset: u64
7   Entry Count: u64
8
9 Data Blocks:
10  Entry: (page_id, lsn, data_length, data[])
11
12 Index (B-tree):
13  page_id -> (offset, lsn)
```

2.3 Four-Layer Read Hierarchy

For a query on branch B at LSN l :

1. **Branch memtable**: In-memory writes for B
2. **Branch Delta SSTables**: On-disk modifications for B
3. **Parent Delta SSTables**: Modifications in parent (created after B 's creation LSN through parent's current LSN at the time of B 's read)
4. **Shared SSTables**: Immutable base data shared across all branches

The search stops at the first layer containing the requested key at the target LSN.

2.4 Merge Strategies

Seven merge strategies are supported for branch merging:

1. **Auto/LastWriteWins**: Most recent modification wins
2. **Ours**: Prefer target branch changes
3. **Theirs**: Prefer source branch changes
4. **Manual**: Detect conflicts, store in conflict table for user resolution
5. **RuleBased**: Per-column/table merge rules
6. **Custom**: User-defined merge function (UDF)
7. **Abort**: Fail on any conflict

Conflict detection uses three-way merge: changes in source and target are compared against the common ancestor (merge base at branch creation LSN).

3 Prior Art

System	Storage	Merge	Strategies
Dolt	Proly trees	Cell-level 3-way	3
Neon	Custom distributed	None	0
PlanetScale	Vitess/MySQL	Schema only	1
Lakebase	COW blocks	None	0
Vela	Block-level COW	None	0
This work	LSM/RocksDB	Page-level 3-way	7

4 Implementation

Implemented in Rust on RocksDB as part of HeliosDB Nano (AGPL-3.0). Module `storage/branch.rs` implements branch metadata, Delta SSTables, the four-layer read path, and merge strategies. Branch creation: <1ms. Storage overhead at creation: 0 bytes (metadata only, 256 bytes for branch struct). Read performance: 97% of main branch. Write performance: 95% of main branch.

References

- [1] DoltHub, “Dolt: Git for data,” 2024.
- [2] Neon, “Database branching,” 2024.
- [3] PlanetScale, “Database branching with three-way merge,” 2024.
- [4] Databricks, “Lakebase branches,” 2025.